

28 - Parents' attitudes towards teaching and learning of Chinese as a heritage language in Japan

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Abstract

The swift rise in the population of children with foreign nationalities in Japan, driven by globalization, underscores the pressing need for education in their mother tongue, or heritage language. Maintaining the heritage language not only fosters children's identity formation and strengthens familial bonds but also promotes bilingualism and contributes to shaping a multicultural society by enhancing proficiency in a second language. Despite its importance, research on heritage language education in Japan remains underdeveloped compared to English-speaking countries like the U.S., Canada, and Australia. This paper aims to address the following questions using a mixed-method approach, including a questionnaire survey and semi-structured interviews with Chinese mothers: 1) What are the attitudes and beliefs of parents regarding the teaching of Chinese as a heritage language? 2) What strategies do parents use to teach the Chinese language at home? The results indicate that maintaining proficiency in Chinese is a valuable tool for fostering a sense of Chinese identity in children. It also highlights that "returning to China with the child regularly" is one of the most used strategies for teaching the language. A cross-sectional study examining both parents' and children's attitudes toward the teaching and learning of Chinese as a heritage language in Japan is necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding.

Keywords: Heritage language education, Bilingualism, Parental attitudes and strategies, Chinese identity formation, Multicultural society in Japan

1. Introduction

Japan has seen shifts in its population dynamics, especially with a significant rise in foreign residents in recent year. According to Immigration Services Agency of Japan, the number of foreign residents in Japan reached approximately 3.4 million as of May 2023^{#1}. Japan's relatively stable economy and high quality of life make it an attractive destination for many Chinese nationals. The relatively close geographical proximity and cultural ties between China and Japan make it a more accessible and appealing option compared to farther English-speaking countries. Over time, the Chinese population has grown exponentially, reaching 820,000 and becoming the largest ethnic community in Japan. This growth has made Japan an important destination for Chinese international migration, especially since the mid-1980s.

The movement of people across countries, driven by internationalization, has introduced new issues and challenges in various fields, including heritage language (HL) education for immigrants and their children. Heritage language education for immigrant children has become an increasingly urgent global issue. Family language policy plays a critical role in maintaining a heritage language, which is largely influenced by parental attitudes and ideologies. Because it "provide a window into parental language ideologies" and "reflect broader societal attitudes and ideologies about both languages and parenting" (King et.al., 2008:907). However, research on Chinese heritage language (CHL) education has predominantly focused on English-speaking countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia, due to the significant increase in Chinese emigration to these regions. In contrast, issues related to CHL education in other parts of the world, such as Japan, have received relatively little attention. Therefore, this study aims to explore the current situation of teaching and learning of Chinese as a heritage language in Japan by addressing the following questions:

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- 1) What are the attitudes and beliefs of parents regarding the teaching of Chinese as a heritage language?
- 2) What strategies do parents use to teach the Chinese language at home?

2. Literature review

2.1 What is a heritage language?

There has been no universally agreed-upon the definition of a HL. Rothman (2009) describes it as "a language spoken at home or otherwise readily available to young children, which is not the dominant language of the larger (national) society" (p. 156). Recently, this term has been broadened to include meanings such as 'community language,' 'home language,' and 'mother tongue/native language' (Shin, 2013; Kagan et al., 2017). Nakajima (2017) refers to it as the "native language of the parents and, for the child, the language inherited from them," but distinguishes it from the mother tongue, stating that "although it is the first language a child learns, much like a mother tongue, it often does not fully develop due to the dominance of the local language" (pp.5-6). Regarding the CHL, Wu (2002) describes it as pertaining to individuals who were exposed to Chinese outside the formal education system, typically within their home or community. Li and Ma (2018) further clarify that the term 'Chinese heritage language' primarily refers to students growing up in countries where the dominant language is not Chinese (p.13). Building on these definitions, this study uses the term 'heritage language' to refer to a language spoken at home, such as Mandarin Chinese, that is not the dominant language of the society.

2.2 Why heritage language education is important?

The importance of teaching and learning of a HL has been addressed in various aspects. Learning and maintaining a heritage language helps individuals connect to their cultural roots, traditions, and family history. It fosters a sense of identity and belonging, allowing them to participate more fully in cultural practices and communicate with family members who may speak the HL. In a study of Chinese American adolescents, Tse (2001) found that those who maintained their heritage language reported a stronger sense of cultural identity and connection to their ethnic community. The study revealed that these adolescents felt more integrated into their cultural group and had a deeper understanding of their cultural practices. Majima et al. (2010) further emphasizes that promoting the HL education will help the foreign pupils to build their self-esteem and establish a positive identity.

Heritage language education plays a crucial role in fostering home-based bilingualism and in turn can enhance cognitive and academic ability such as language learning. Cummins' theory of language interdependence emphasizes that the cognitive and academic skills developed in a child's first language can positively impact the learning and proficiency of a second language (Cummins 1980, 1984). Cummins (2001:17) further argues that "the level of development of children's mother tongue is a strong predictor of their second language development".

Foreign language education in Japan tends to focus heavily on English, often neglecting the importance of multilingual education. As Mu (2008) and Takahashi (2019) have mentioned, language education for foreign children in Japan has traditionally prioritized Japanese language acquisition and "adaptation" education, while support for their mother tongues and academic studies is often overlooked. Kubota (2019) further warns that the focus on English, given its role as a global lingua franca in international communication and business, has resulted in insufficient promotion of other languages. Many issues related to HL teaching, such as securing resources for studying HLs remain unaddressed (Saito, 2005). He (2010) calls for the urgency of HL research, noting that there is a significant gap in understanding how parents implement native language education for their children and the challenges they face.

3. Methodology

3.1 Instrument

In this study, a mixed-method approach was utilized, combining a questionnaire survey with semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire featured both multiple-choice and open-ended questions, aimed at exploring attitudes toward CHL education and various teaching methods. The semi-structured interviews were conducted to obtain detailed and in-depth insights from participants about their experiences and perspectives on CHL teaching and learning.

3.2 Participants

A snowball sampling method was employed, utilizing referrals from acquaintances. The study included 14 Chinese mothers, aged 30 to 49, residing in Fukuoka City, Japan. Among the participants, four are married to Japanese husbands, and ten are married to Chinese husbands. All participants hold a bachelor's degree. The primary reason for their move to Japan was to pursue studies, except for one participant who relocated for marriage. All their children were born in Japan. One participant works part-time, while the remaining are full-time homemakers.

3.3 Procedures for data collection

Upon data collection, participants received both written and verbal explanations detailing the research objectives, methods, and procedures for handling data. Consent for recording was also obtained. Data collection involved a Zoom interview lasting approximately one hour. The interview was recorded, transcribed, and subsequently coded using a thematic coding approach.

4. Results

4.1 Strong attitudes toward the teaching and learning of CHL.

The questionnaire survey aimed to uncover the attitudes and beliefs of parents regarding the teaching and learning of CHL at home. All 14 participants demonstrated strong attitudes toward CHL instruction. Figure 1 shows their responses, with numbers and percentages in brackets representing the count of respondents and their respective percentages.

1. To communicate with my child in my native language to foster an emotional connection (14, 100%)
2. It is important to study Chinese language and culture thoroughly to preserve our roots and identity (9, 64%)
3. To be able to communicate with relatives and friends in China (9, 64%).
4. The Chinese language will be important for future studies and career opportunities. (9, 64%).
5. Being multilingual can enhance one's personal value (7, 50%).
6. Preparing my child return to China for studying or working in the future (7, 28.5%).
7. The Chinese language has rich expressiveness, convenient use of characters, and profound meaning (1, 7.1%).

Figure 1. Attitudes and beliefs of parents regarding the teaching and learning of CHL

Turning to the results of the semi-structured interviews on attitudes toward CHL education and specific teaching methods, a 42-year-old mother of two daughters mentioned that,

I hope my child can learn Chinese. As a Chinese mother, I don't want to waste this valuable language resource. I want to build my child's confidence in speaking Chinese and help them take pride in being bilingual.

Another mother, in her 40s with one daughter, said:

I consider myself to be more old-fashioned. I believe that if you are a Chinese, you should never forget your roots. No matter where you go, even if you are born in Japan, you are still Chinese. Therefore, learning Chinese and understanding Chinese culture are essential.

As illustrated by these two extracts, both mothers had strong attitudes toward teaching the language, with a greater emphasis on Chinese culture, history, and maintaining their roots.

4.2 The most used strategies for the teaching and learning of CHL

Figure 2 presents the most used strategies for teaching Chinese. As illustrated in the figure, the most frequently employed strategies are as follows:

1. Regularly returning to China with my children (14 answered, 100%).
2. Keeping the practice of speaking Chinese with my children as much as possible (13, 93%).
3. Encouraging my children to interact with family members in China online (11, 78.6%).
4. Encouraging my children to watch Chinese TV shows, anime, etc. (10, 71.4%).
5. Encouraging them to listen to or read Chinese storybooks using apps. (10, 71.4%).
6. Buying Chinese storybooks for my children (9, 64.3%).
7. Enrolling them in Chinese language classes (8, 57.1%).
8. Teaching my children using Chinese textbooks myself (6, 42.9%).
9. Hiring a tutor for private lessons (5, 35.7%).
10. Enrolling them in online classes (5, 35.7%).
11. Asking grandparents to come to Japan to care for the child (3, 21.4%).

Figure 2. Most used strategies for the teaching and learning of CHL

As shown in Figure 2, the most used strategies for teaching and learning of CHL were “Regularly returning to China with my children” (14, 100%), followed by “Keeping the practice of speaking Chinese with the children” (13, 93%), “Encouraging my children to interact with families in China as much as possible” (11, 78.6%), “Encouraging my children to watch Chinese TV shows, anime, etc.” (10, 71.4%) and “Encouraging them to listen to or read Chinese storybooks using apps” (10, 71.4%) respectively.

The effectiveness of “Regularly returning to China with my children” is also concretely reflected in the interview, as illustrated below:

I think the most effective way to improve your child’s Chinese language skills is to take them back to China for a month or two. Let them play with other children, enjoy their favorite foods, and watch Chinese cartoons without any stress. Don’t even worry about it; just let your child play with other children, eat the foods and watch the Chinese cartoons they like. (a 30-year-old mother with one daughter)

...we used to go back almost every year, and sometimes her dad would take her to their grandparents’ house. I believe this is really the best way to learn the language. The child can experience and hear many things that they can’t in Japan... (a 40-year-old mother of two sons)

5. Discussion

The first two responses regarding attitudes toward the teaching and learning of Chinese as a heritage language indicated a desire to foster a close emotional bond with their children using their native language. They also highlighted the importance of maintaining and strengthening social connections with relatives and friends in China, underscoring a commitment to preserving cultural and linguistic heritage. This reflects a positive attitude toward both maintaining emotional connections and emphasizing the value of cultural preservation in parenting. These views support the claims that promoting heritage language education helps pupils build self-esteem and establish a positive identity (Majima et al., 2010; Tian and Sakurai, 2017) and that such education enhances children’s awareness of their identity (Sasaoka, 2022).

Pertaining to the most used strategies for teaching Chinese as a heritage language, “regularly returning to China with my children” was ranked highest. This strategy provides immersive language learning, cultural exposure, and social interaction, leveraging the immersion effect to enhance language acquisition and cultural understanding. When children are in China, they benefit from a real-life context that encourages them to use the language naturally. Being in China also provides opportunities to experience the culture and interact with local people, which facilitates their language learning. This approach underscores the importance of acquiring a mother tongue during early

childhood or youth. As Au et al. (2008:1009) mentioned, “childhood language experience can remain accessible after years of disuse.”

The geographical convenience of Japan plays a significant role in facilitating heritage language education. The flight time between Japan and China typically ranges from about 2 to 4 hours, which is considerably shorter and more affordable compared to flights from North America or Europe. This makes regular travel between Japan and China an effective option for heritage language education. In contrast, traveling from North America or Europe to China can be burdensome due to longer flight times and higher costs, which can be a significant financial strain for families in these more distant regions. Therefore, while regular travel between Japan and China is a feasible model for teaching Chinese heritage language (CHL), similar strategies might also be beneficial in neighboring countries such as Korea or Southeast Asian countries.

The latter three strategies reflect the use of IT technologies, particularly since the outbreak of COVID-19, which led to the development of various online learning tools and educational activities despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. This result supports Said (2021)'s view that regular use of technology can be an important and effective tool for sustaining family ties and maintaining heritage language. It also addresses King (2022)'s call to explore the role of modern technology in heritage language education.

4. Conclusion

Both quantitative and qualitative surveys showed that all Chinese mothers had a strong attitude towards the teaching and learning of CHL. Building a strong sense of Chinese culture, roots, and identity were major concerns for parents. Additionally, the utilitarian value of the language was also crucial. The second major finding was that consistently traveling back to China with their children is one of the most used strategies for teaching the language and is considered the most effective approach. Other effective strategies include maintaining regular conversations in Chinese with the children and promoting interactions between the children and family members through online platforms. For future research, a cross-sectional study examining both parents' and children's attitudes towards the teaching and learning of Chinese as a heritage language in Japan is necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding.

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